

AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines creative pedagogical activity as a heuristic component of personality development, the stages of its formation, criteria for pedagogical creativity, spheres of creative activity of a teacher, self-education and self-realization of a teacher.

The article highlights the issues of implementing innovative technologies of managing the educational process based on a creative approach in the professional education system, expanding the possibilities of training competitive specialists by using modern pedagogical technologies. Creativity (Creative approach) as a personality quality is the ability to create qualitatively new material and spiritual values that are valuable for people and for society. Teaching is one of the most creative fields. It has a lot in common with other creative areas of human activity, but there are also unique features that are unique to it. A creative approach to business and true mastery presupposes an individual style of activity of the teacher, in which the strongest aspects of his personality are realized.

“...The translation of scientific truths into the living experience of creative work is the most difficult area of contact between science and practice. A discovery made by a scientist, when it comes to life in human relationships, in a living outburst of thoughts and emotions, appears before the teacher as a complex task that can be solved in many ways, and in the choice of a method, in the embodiment of theoretical truths in living human emotions, lies the creative process. [5, p. 5]

Creativity is one of the amazing phenomena of human activity. Outstanding academician V.A. Engelhard wrote that creativity in its original source is the result of an innate, physiological need, “the result of a certain instinct, felt as powerfully as the need of a bird to sing or the desire of a fish to rise against the flow of a stormy mountain river.” Indeed,

a person, without realizing it, introduces elements of creativity into any work, even the most seemingly distant from creativity [6, p. 232].

Many scientists studying the problem of creativity are inclined to think that creativity is the essence of human activity, and heuristic activity is a component of creativity. A modern teacher needs to develop creativity, as it is the main indicator of creative professional competence.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the creative nature of pedagogical activity, to determine working methods that influence the increase in the creative potential of teachers, to consider the stages of formation of a teacher's creative personality, the results of his creative activity, and to determine the criteria for pedagogical creativity.

Every day, in different parts of the world, the school bell calls millions of teachers to their classrooms. They energetically walk along the school corridors, the door to the classroom opens, and... a great sacrament begins, whose name is pedagogical creativity.

Pedagogical work is never uncreative, since each student is a separate and unique personality, circumstances that are dictated by events and time, the personality of the teacher himself, and any pedagogical decision must be based on these always non-standard factors. It follows that teaching activity is a manifestation of constant, versatile creativity.

Creativity is everything that surrounds us, bright colorful nature, the rustle of leaves, the sound of rain... First, it is the process and result of creative activity: culture, art, knowledge, work, beauty. Creativity is the main, leading component of pedagogical activity and is a decisive factor in the teacher's advancement to the heights of his pedagogical skills. A teacher is not a profession, it is a way of life. The modern rhythm of life requires continuous professional growth, a creative attitude to work, and dedication from the teacher. A creative teacher is "the one who opens, makes wise and approves".

Teaching creativity. Is it even possible to teach this? The outstanding Soviet psychologist L. S. Vygotsky wrote: "It is impossible to teach the creative act of art, but this does not mean at all that the educator cannot contribute to its formation and emergence. Through consciousness we penetrate into the unconscious; we can, in a certain way, organize conscious processes in such a way that through them we can evoke unconscious processes" [7, p. 327].

In the 21st century, with rapid changes in economic, political and social situations, as well as an abundance of professions requiring creative abilities, creativity occupies an essential place in the learning process of new generations.

Education is a process of both learning and upbringing. The new era values an individual who is ready and able to make decisions and be responsible for them in every area of life. Therefore, at the center of the work of every teacher, educator, teacher-organizer, a guideline should be placed on the formation of an individual "educational trajectory" for each child.

In the modern world, more than ever before, the level of integrity of society depends on identifying the abilities of each individual in various sectors of life. The intellectual potential of society as a whole and individually of each member, the development of creative abilities directly depends on the level of education of the individual, who at school not only receives certain knowledge and develops certain skills and abilities, but also knows how to

use them creatively and make independent decisions. Hence, every teacher must take into account real social needs and direct his efforts to developing the creative potential of his students, which contributes to the self-realization of each child and the progress of society as a whole.

The only opportunity for a child to keep up with the kaleidoscope of changes in society is through true creative adaptation to the conditions of society. And the teacher, like no one else, must provide it, provide conditions for self-realization of the individual according to his potential capabilities and interests.

The optimal forms of working with students according to this problem at school are:

- design;
- scientific research;
- creative activity.

Project activity is a complex of interrelated actions that develop around the theoretical and practical parts of the project. The project provides an opportunity to develop creatively and use in practice the knowledge acquired during preparation for project activities.

For example, this academic year the school is actively introducing such a form of work as project activity "Individual Project". Children are encouraged to create their own biology or ecology projects throughout the school year. The result of such project activities were leaflets, posters, presentations and the project work itself produced by students.

The scientific research activity of students at our educational institution consists of several stages: working with scientific literature, developing hypotheses, forming ideas, developing a work plan, organizing practical work on the research topic, processing, design and presentation of research results.

Creative activity is the most difficult area of working with children. She foresees the creation of conditions for identifying the student's abilities in independent work. To create a full-fledged developmental environment, the school runs clubs.

And one more thing: no matter how tempting it may be to hold an event like last year without changing anything, you should always remember that "repetition is the mother of learning, but the death sentence of creativity."

Therefore, when planning and implementing educational and educational work, it is necessary:

- work on positive emotions, as they are an essential element of creativity;
- create conditions for proper provision of self-realization of the student's personality;
- help the child decide not only who to be, but what to be, how to arrange his own individual way of life, choose his main trajectory.

For what could be better for the formation of a personality, its creative development, than a feeling of success and self-worth from the results of one's work?

It can be considered that the method of creative projects is now becoming relevant, the purpose of which is to promote the independent formation of intellectual, social and general cultural knowledge and skills of students, to promote the development of such skills as:

- initiative;
- skills of working in pairs, in groups;

- logical thinking, problem vision;
- decision making, obtaining and using information;
- independent planning of plans;
- development of communication skills.

The method of creative projects is aimed at creative self-realization of the individual in the process of training and education. When applying the project method, the psychological and pedagogical aspects of student creativity are most clearly manifested during preparation, consistently practiced skills, the active use of creativity algorithms, and the opportunity for students to manipulate the time allotted for preparing a project.

It is important to remember that the project product is not the goal; the project itself and the process of its implementation is a way to develop students' creative abilities.

A creative teacher is constantly searching for optimal didactic, educational, methodological, managerial and any other pedagogical solutions. The focus on finding the most effective approaches to any problems that arise among these teachers is so great that we can say that they have a clearly defined goal reflex, about which the outstanding Russian physiologist I. P. Pavlov wrote the following: "The goal reflex is of great vital importance, it is the basic form of life energy in each of us. The life of only one is red and clear who strives all his life for a goal that is constantly achieved, but never achievable, or who moves from one goal to another with the same ardor. If each of us cherishes this reflex within ourselves as the most precious part of our being, if parents and all teachers of all ranks make it their main task to strengthen and develop this reflex in the masses under their care, if our society and statehood open up wide opportunities for the practice of this reflex, then we will become what we should and can be." [8, p. 310] It is obvious that it is creative teachers who realize this cherished dream better than others; They, more than anyone else, have a developed reflex of purpose, associated precisely with the need to create, to create something new, more effective, optimal at a given stage, ideal in the future.

As life shows, success in teaching accompanies only those teachers whose universal human qualities and general personal culture are highly developed. The constant development of the general culture of the individual is a categorical requirement for any teacher, but especially for a creative one, since it is the general culture of a person that is the foundation on which didactic, educational, methodological, managerial - any creative pedagogical technology is built [9, p.102]. Analysis of practice, life itself convincingly shows that even with a teacher's developed ability for creativity, but with an insufficient level of general culture, his discoveries and inventions do not give either a teaching or educational effect, and often lead to negative results.

In connection with the level characteristics of pedagogical creativity, the question arises about the creativity of young teachers who do not have sufficient pedagogical and professional experience. Pedagogical experience can be widespread and advanced. Through trial and error, teaching experience and pedagogical creativity are identified. The words "advanced pedagogical experience" is used in a broad and narrow sense (M.N. Skatkin). In a broad sense, excellence is understood as the high skill of a teacher. However, his experience may not contain anything new or original, but he is a model for young teachers. In this sense,

the achieved pedagogical excellence represents advanced experience worthy of dissemination.

Best practices include only those practices that contain elements of creative search, novelty, originality, what is otherwise called innovation. Such pedagogical experience is especially valuable because it opens new paths in pedagogical science and educational practice. Therefore, it is the best practices that are subject to analysis, generalization, and dissemination. It is often difficult to draw a line between simple pedagogical skill and innovators, because, having mastered well-known principles and methods, the teacher usually does not stop there. Finding and using more and more original techniques or in a new way, effectively combining old ones, the master teacher gradually becomes a true innovator.

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